

MareGraph

Towards an Interoperable Marine Knowledge Graph

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Lead Author (Org)	Giorgia Lodi (CNR-ISTC), Alessandro Russo (CNR-ISTC)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Andrea Giovanni Nuzzolese (CNR-ISTC), Francesco Poggi (CNR-ISTC), Joanna Goley (VLIZ), Marc Portier (VLIZ), Laurian Van Maldeghem (VLIZ), Bart Vanhoorne (VLIZ), Stefanie Dekeyzer (VLIZ)
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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
DUL	DOLCE + DnS Ultralite (ontology)
LOD	Linked Open Data
ODP	Ontology Design Pattern
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PROV-O	The PROVenance Ontology
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SKOS-XL	Simple Knowledge Organization System – eXtension for Labels
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VLIZ	Flanders Marine Institute
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
XD	eXtreme Design

Executive Summary

This document presents the initial versions of the ontologies created in MAREGRAPH, which are needed to represent the data stored in the WoRMS database in Linked Open Data, thus increasing semantic interoperability for identified high-value data.

The document provides a description of the ontologies produced, which can be viewed as modular ontology modules linked together, forming the so-called APHIA ontology network. The modularisation approach that covers different aspects of marine species data (e.g., taxa names, geographical distributions, attributes and traits) allows for flexibility and adaptation of the data models to specific needs.

The network currently consists of four domain OWL ontology modules and a top-level OWL ontology, the purpose of which is both to link the various domain entities and to define all those entities that are independent of the specific domain but necessary to fulfil modelling requirements. The top-level ontology is based on well-known foundational ontologies available at the state of the art (e.g., DOLCE).

The document also describes the methodology that was applied to achieve the result. The methodology is contextualised within the processes outlined in D2.1; it involves conducting a state-of-the-art analysis on the existing standards, ontologies and vocabularies of the domain, which this document discusses, and collecting requirements. The requirements that were gathered during the first year of the project in various forms, such as use cases, competency questions (questions to be asked about the data), bottom-up analysis of data from WoRMS, are summarised in the deliverable.

Finally, a reference example of Linked Open Data for a specific marine species is introduced in the document to provide a guide on the use of the ontology modules in the presence of real data taken from the WoRMS system.

The results included in this document are preparatory to the technical activities of WP4 and WP5. These activities will also be necessary to refine the ontology modules introduced here for the production of the final version of the ontologies envisaged in the subsequent deliverable D3.2.

The various versions of the ontologies are publicly available on the github repository of the project (<https://github.com/MareGraph-EU/assets/tree/main>).

Controlled vocabularies for certain entities identified in ontologies have yet to be prepared. However, the document highlights those entities whose individuals may be good candidates to be concepts of controlled vocabularies built using the SKOS Web standard.

1 Introduction

One of the main objectives of the MAREGRAPH project is to augment the semantic interoperability of identified high value datasets in the fishery domain. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to create a robust and interoperable semantic framework that can serve as the foundation for an open marine knowledge graph, aiming to make high value marine datasets readily discoverable, accessible, interoperable and understandable, and reusable to anyone (i.e., make them FAIR according to the well-known open science FAIR principles¹).

In order to increase the semantic interoperability of data, it is necessary to pay attention to its true meaning and underlying context. In fact, without ambiguities, data can then be better analysed, leading to reliable inferences and better decision-making.

However, the implementation of semantic interoperability is not an easy task and requires the creation of consensus between different stakeholders on shared data models and meanings.

This deliverable outlines the preliminary results of this process we started in MAREGRAPH in order to build a semantic framework capable of supporting an effective production of Linked Open Data for high value open datasets identified in the project. These results are the outcome of various discussions and compromises reached with both external project stakeholders, and VLIZ domain experts who provide the datasets to be transformed in Linked Open Data.

In particular, the deliverable discusses the methodology that was followed in the overall organisational process identified in OSLO and introduced in WP2, as well as the state of the art that we conducted to arrive at the definition of a network of ontological modules that we called the APHIA network.

Despite an important effort has been done to create ontologies that could satisfy the specific requirements dictated by the WoRMS database, i.e., the first open datasets we considered in the project, there are still some challenges to be faced that can be summarized as follows.

Firstly, it is important to test and validate the ontologies against the data of WoRMS, in real linked open data production pipelines, but also in wider contexts where the same ontologies could be required and thus reused². In this sense, this preliminary result is an important milestone to guide the technical activities of WP4 and WP5 and to understand other needs beyond those specific from VLIZ and its WoRMS system.

Secondly, providing SHACL shapes starting from OWL restrictions included in the ontologies here described can be an added value to validate the data itself. Thirdly, a set of individuals of already identified classes of the ontologies can be viewed as concepts of controlled

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² VLIZ and CNR-ISTC are involved in an industrial project with DG MARE for the development of the EU commercial designations information system of the fishery and aquaculture products marketed in EU. In this context, Linked Open Data must be published and there are currently on-going works to re-use as much as possible some ontology modules developed in MAREGRAPH.

vocabularies. This entails that one of the next steps to be targeted is the creation of such vocabularies.

Finally, reaching a consensus in the community about the semantics of the data is a crucial step towards a possible higher acceptance and adoption of the ontologies we defined. In this regard, as planned in the OSLO process of WP2, a public review on the results described in this document will be open after the submission of the deliverable itself.

The rest of this document is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the methodology we followed. Section 3 discusses about the state of the art, while Section 4 present the requirement elicitation. Section 5 is the core of the deliverable since it presents all the ontologies that have been produced so far. Section 6 discusses a possible use of the ontologies using real data from WoRMS for an identified species and finally, Section 7 concludes the deliverable.

2 Methodology for ontology design and engineering

For the design and implementation of the ontology modules presented in this document, we followed the general process as described in the deliverable D2.1 within which we delineated a technical methodology for ontology design and engineering.

Specifically, we set up an internal working group with the business partner (VLIZ) to define a first version of a Charter that has been published in the MAREGRAPH website³. The Charter is a declaration of intents for starting the development of ontologies (or semantic assets). It includes the objective of MAREGRAPH, the high value datasets identified in the project, the initial use cases acknowledged by the business partner, and a possible tentative schedule for engaging with external stakeholders (community building) in the ontologies definition process.

In the Charter, we reported the plan for three different workshops with external communities: a first business workshop where the project and its objectives were presented along with the methodology we wanted to follow for the creation of the ontologies and controlled vocabularies; two thematic workshops on the WoRMS data, where the WoRMS system was explained with the list of data to be potentially transformed in Linked Open Data according to some semantic assets. During these two thematic workshops a discussion about the state of the art of existing ontologies for the reference domain (reported in Section 3) was done and initial proposals for modelling the data (so-called draft interim specifications of the process discussed in the deliverable D2.1) were presented in order to collect feedback to be used in successive steps to continuously refine the ontologies design, in a pure agile and iterative manner.

In this context, we technically developed the first versions of the ontologies for WoRMS using a specific methodology named eXtreme Design (see also [2]) that is described in the next subsection.

2.1 Ontology Engineering Approach – the XD methodology

The eXtreme Design methodology is collaborative, as it is planned in the OSLO process described in the deliverable D2.1, and shown in a high-level process in Figure 1.

It requires the joint work of teams of *ontology engineers* (ontology design team of Figure 1) and *domain experts*, these latter also coming from the data provider of the project. Moreover, the methodology is incremental and iterative, as the design pairs integrate the modules produced by the other pairs to obtain incremental releases of the ontology.

³ <https://www.maregraph.eu/>

Figure 1: Ontology design and development process

In Figure 1 we illustrate the most important stages that constitute the XD methodology. The first stage is the collection of requirements and their definition. Requirements can be collected in different forms, from use cases to competency questions definition (see Section 4) up to data extraction from the database (using a more bottom-up approach). Once a set of requirements has been identified, ontology design is done by going through a state-of-the-art analysis of existing ontologies and so-called Ontology Design Patterns (ODPs).

XD, in fact, relies on the concept of ODPs, which are reusable modelling solutions created to solve recurring ontology modelling problems. We decided to use an ODPs-based approach because there is evidence [3] that the reuse of ODPs can (i) speed up the ontology design process, (ii) ease design choices, (iii) produce more effective results in terms of ontology quality, and (iv) boost (semantic) interoperability, this latter one of the main objectives of the MAREGRAPH project.

In these analyses that trigger the design, top-level (or upper or foundational) ontologies play an important role. These types of ontologies define general concepts (e.g., System, Agent, Topic, Region, etc.) and relationships (e.g., part of, causality, participation) *“that are meant to be basic and universal to ensure generality and expressiveness for a wide range of domains”* [4]. They provide a specific view, with their defined logical axioms, of the world and could be very helpful to: i) understand the semantic essence of what is to be represented; ii) connect different entities in different ontologies; iii) define general elements that are independent of the specific domain.

In the project, we decided to adopt variants of a very famous foundational ontology which is DOLCE [1]. This brought us to model a top-level ontology that also extends some of DOLCE’s general concepts with others necessary to meet the gathered requirements (e.g., Identifier, Name).

In the design and implementation phase we also apply both a direct and indirect re-use approach of ontologies already publicly available.

With the term direct re-use we mean the practice for which when building a new ontology, existing ontologies as a whole or in parts are *directly* reused by taking classes/concepts and properties from diverse ontologies, usually based on similarities between names of other ontologies entities/properties. If not applied carefully, the selection of the reused properties

and classes may cause semantic inconsistencies with the original semantics of the reused terms. This practice, quite common in pure Linked Open Data projects, might bring to create so-called “Frankenstein ontologies” [5] .

In contrast, we the term indirect re-use we mean the practice for which when building a new ontology, existing ontologies are *indirectly* reused by defining semantic alignments and mappings to enable interoperability. In this case, the ontology under development has its own well-defined semantics based on the requirements gathered, and the alignment axioms are added, also as possible separate artefacts from the main ontology under design.

For more details on the meaning of direct and indirect re-use of semantic assets in literature, the interested readers can refer to [6] .

Table 1 and Table 2 present the advantages and disadvantages of these two approaches, respectively.

Table 1: The pros and cons of the direct re-use of existing ontologies

Direct Reuse Pros	Direct Reuse Cons
It can maximize the reusability and interoperability when reusing standard, authoritative ontologies that are “trust” and “understood” (in a domain)	There could be a semantic misalignment among reused ontologies and with respect to domain requirements. In fact, it happens quite often that reused ontologies may build on different assumptions and lead to inconsistencies when combined with others.
It can help saving time and effort when concepts, relationships and axioms <i>fully</i> satisfy domain requirements	It enables a strong dependency on and coupling with external resources. This also means that if the re-used ontology changes or becomes unavailable over time, the entire semantics of the ontology being created on the basis of the direct reuse can be fully compromised
It enhances the acceptance and adoption of the new ontology within the relevant community	Possible modifications to the reused ontology may not be feasible or “appropriate” from a semantic perspective

Table 2: The pros and cons of the indirect re-use of existing ontologies

Indirect Reuse Pros	Indirect Reuse Cons
It allows for a full control over the semantics of the ontology, with <i>stability</i> , <i>robustness</i> and <i>sustainability</i> of fundamental concepts and relationships of the target domain	There could be a potential effort to create and maintain over time alignments and mappings
It enables high flexibility and multiple integration possibilities, with specialization of concepts and relationships (of both domain-specific and general purpose or foundational ontologies) to meet specific requirements	There could be potential challenges when aligning ontologies with different levels of semantic granularity

It preserves <i>interoperability</i> with existing models and community acceptance, without reinventing the wheel	The reuse and alignments may not be immediately apparent or obvious to non-experts
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In the design of the ontologies described in this deliverable we decided to use a hybrid approach: when actual standards and Web recommendations from standardisation bodies (i.e., ISO, W3C) include classes and properties corresponding to a strong semantic alignment with what we want to express to meet specific requirements, we use *directly* them. For all the remaining cases, we apply an *indirect reuse* approach, with semantic alignments axioms included in the same ontology artefact being developed in MAREGRAPH. We have not yet reached a consensus on producing semantic alignments axioms in a separate file with respect to the ontology that has to be designed and implemented. We will target this methodological approach in the upcoming releases of the ontologies.

Once all the elements to be represented have been specified, a modularisation approach is used. This modularisation implies the production of several ontological modules with the top-level ontology being the glue to keep them organised together in a network. This organisation of knowledge usually also helps in future maintenance procedures with respect to data peculiarities: data may have different management procedures and different update frequencies that may have an impact on the management of their semantic representations.

Finally, it is important to report that when designing ontologies ontology designers are used to sketch them in some graphical representations. There are different types of graphical notations to be used in order to represent OWL ontologies. Examples include Graffoo [7] and Graphol [8]. Other practices suggest the use of UML class diagrams to represent ontologies, although UML expressivity is not comparable to that offered by languages born with the purpose to create ontologies like OWL.

The graphical representation can be used to document the semantics being implemented, but also as a technical starting point from which to derive the ontology source code, using standards such as RDFSchema and OWL, or the HTML representation of the ontology.

We decided to use Graffoo and UML for the graphical representations that are included in this deliverable. At the moment, these are utilised in the communication between ontology designers and internal and external domain experts, and for documentation purposes. An internal discussion is on-going about their role in the ontology implementation process.

3 Ontologies and data models for biodiversity information

Over the years, various models and ontologies were designed and proposed for the representation and interchange of information about species and, more in general, scientific data on biodiversity. The development of such models is strictly related to the evolution of biodiversity informatics, i.e., the application of informatics techniques to biodiversity information, such as taxonomy, biogeography or ecology. Rich data models are in fact at the heart of biodiversity information systems, such as the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), which aim at supporting the process of comprehensively cataloguing and organising biological taxa and their scientific names, traits, ecological interactions, distribution, and other biological data, often through the integration of information from diverse sources.

A comprehensive data model for representing biodiversity information typically encompasses several core elements:

- **Taxa:** this includes the classification of organisms into taxonomic groups with hierarchical relationships, as well as references to authoritative taxonomic sources. This information allows representing the hierarchical structure of biological classification, ranging from broader categories like kingdom and phylum to narrower categories like genus and species.
- **Scientific names:** the formal scientific names used to denote taxa. They typically adhere to the rules of nomenclature established by reference organisations in international codes of nomenclature. The representation and management of scientific names also requires dealing with synonyms, homonyms and other relationships between names and their role as labels for taxa.
- **Identifiers:** to support information exchange and avoid ambiguities, taxa and names typically have unique identifiers within the reference system, facilitating unambiguous reference and integration with other data sources and systems.
- **Traits, attributes and other properties:** this includes observable quantitative or qualitative characteristics of organisms and attributes or properties associated with taxa, such as morphology, behaviour, physiology, life history attributes, and ecological interactions (such as predation, parasitism, etc.).
- **Distribution:** distribution data records where organisms are found geographically, potentially including information on habitats, geographic ranges, species origin and other details.
- **References and sources:** this includes references to authoritative sources, scientific literature, taxonomic databases, and other data providers to support the validity and traceability of taxonomic information and provide context and provenance for biodiversity data.

As many authors have observed (e.g., [10] [11] [12]), scientific names represent the crucial element in being able to link together information from different sources and disciplines (e.g., literature, geography, genetics, etc.); at the same time, this might also pose problems, e.g.,

due to the fact that species have received different names over time and the same name has been used for different species. On one side scientific names form the basis for referring to species and they label biodiversity information across the entire spectrum of biodiversity knowledge, but on the other side scientific names can be unstable, imperfect and potentially ambiguous identifiers for taxa (as discussed for example in [13] [14] [15]). As this dichotomy between scientific names and taxa plays an important role, it represents one of the core aspects considered in the main data models and ontologies presented and summarised hereafter.

The goal of this section is thus to introduce and summarise the primary aspects of the main data models used to represent and exchange biodiversity-related data. While our main focus is on ontological models, we also consider existing relevant models that do not necessarily have an ontological representation.

3.1 Darwin Core (DwC)

Darwin Core⁴ is the de facto standard for representing and sharing biodiversity information [17] . Conceived as an extension of Dublin Core, it is part of the biodiversity information standards maintained by the Taxonomic Databases Working Group (TDWG). Darwin Core (DwC) defines and makes available a glossary of terms (basically classes and properties), definitions and guidelines for representing taxa, their occurrence in nature (as documented by observations, specimens, samples) and related information. DwC is widely used in biodiversity informatics and serves as a foundation for data sharing among various platforms, including biodiversity databases, research projects, and other initiatives. An overview of the main categories or classes of information that can be represented using Darwin Core is provided in Figure 2. The available classes or categories are subject to revisions and extensions, and additional classes or categories were defined since the initial release; some of them are directly "borrowed" from Dublin Core. For the full set of current Darwin Core terms with their descriptions, please refer to <https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/>.

⁴ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

Record-level Terms	Dublin Core terms, institutions, collections, nature of data record	Simple Darwin Core (flat)
Occurrence	evidence of species in nature, observers, behavior, associated media, references.	
Event	sampling protocols and methods, date, time, field notes	
Location	geography, locality descriptions, spatial data	
Identification	linkage between Taxon and Occurrence	
Taxon	scientific names, vernacular names, names usages, taxon concepts, and the relationships between them	
GeologicalContext	geologic time, chrono-stratigraphy, biostratigraphy, lithostratigraphy	
ResourceRelationship	explicit relationships between identified resources (e.g., one organism to another, taxon to location, etc.)	Generic Darwin Core (relational)
MeasurementOrFact	measurements, facts, characteristics, assertions, references	

Figure 2: Overview of Darwin Core categories for representing biodiversity data. Source [16].

Fundamental to our analysis and discussion is DwC's Taxon class, whose definition and properties are shown in Figure 3.

Taxon

taxonID

scientificNameID

acceptedNameUsageID

parentNameUsageID

originalNameUsageID

nameAccordingToID

namePublishedInID

taxonConceptID

scientificName

acceptedNameUsage

parentNameUsage

originalNameUsage

nameAccordingTo

namePublishedIn

namePublishedInYear

higherClassification

kingdom

phylum

class

order

superfamily

family

subfamily

tribe

subtribe

genus

genericName

subgenus

infragenericEpithet

specificEpithet

infraspecificEpithet

cultivarEpithet

taxonRank

verbatimTaxonRank

scientificNameAuthorship

vernacularName

nomenclaturalCode

taxonomicStatus

nomenclaturalStatus

taxonRemarks

Taxon Class

Identifier <http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/Taxon>

Definition A group of organisms (sensu http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0100026) considered by taxonomists to form a homogeneous unit.

Figure 3: Definition and properties for Dwc Taxon class

In DwC, the Taxon class plays a crucial role in describing taxonomic information related to organisms, as it allows representing taxonomic entities such as species, genera, families, and other taxonomic ranks within biodiversity datasets. The Taxon class includes properties for representing both taxonomic and nomenclatural information, such as scientific names, taxon ranks, taxonomic status and hierarchical relationships between taxa (indicating parent-child

relationships within taxonomic classifications), as well as vernacular names and references to sources. Darwin Core thus conflates taxonomy and nomenclature information within a single class, reflecting the pragmatic approach taken to address the practical needs of biodiversity data sharing and integration. While such an approach may offer practical benefits for biodiversity data management and exchange, it may not fully capture the complexities and nuances of the domain in case an explicit distinction has to be made between taxa and the names used to label or refer to them.

A detailed usage guide is also provided on how to use Darwin Core for RDF data⁵. Nevertheless, the RDF guide basically highlights that the usage of classes and properties generally follows a loosely specified semantics. So while in principle *“any Darwin Core class IRI MAY be used as a value for rdf:type”*, DwC does not declare domains for its property terms and the application of properties to instances of classes presented in reference guide has to be considered as a suggestion. More in details, when it comes to the description of a taxonomic entity, the RDF guide explicitly states that for the properties listed in Figure 3 *“it is NOT RECOMMENDED to use these as properties of dwc:Taxon instances”*. The guide further states that *“the object properties necessary to relate dwc:Taxon instances to name entities, references, parent taxa, and child taxa do not exist and the exact relationship between taxonomic entities such as taxon concepts, protonyms, taxon name usages, etc. has not been established using RDF. So the creation of functional dwc:Taxon instances described using RDF is not possible at the present time”*. On one side the loosely defined semantics of the properties allows reusing them in different settings, but on the other side the guidelines basically suggest that DwC is not to be considered as a ready-to-use straightforward ontology for representing taxonomic entities in RDF. To partially overcome this limitation, the guide suggests considering the TDWG Taxon Concept Transfer Schema (TCS) standard for representing taxonomic entities; however, TCS is defined as an XML schema only, without explicit support for RDF (see section below for additional details on TCS).

Regardless of these aspects, DwC plays a central role in the representation of biodiversity-related data and this was taken into account in the design of our ontology modules. Moreover, the importance and potential reuse of DwC will further emerge when we will address the representation of species observation in relation to EurOBIS.

3.2 Taxon Concept Schema (TCS) and TCS 2

Taxon Concept Schema (TCS) is a TDWG standard⁶ defined for representing and exchanging taxonomic data. It was designed for representing taxon concepts as defined in various sources like published classifications, revisions, and databases. It is technically defined as an XML Schema which specifies the structure for XML documents used to transfer these concepts. The schema allows representing taxa by either explicitly detailing all defining components, or by using Globally Unique Identifiers (GUIDs) that refer to existing defined concepts, if and when available. TCS makes an explicit distinction between taxon names and taxon concepts, owing to the observations that one name may be used to denote several concepts, and that names are governed by nomenclature rules and codes that are separate from those for

⁵ Darwin Core RDF guide - <https://dwc.tdwg.org/rdf/>

⁶ <http://www.tdwg.org/standards/117>

concepts. The overall approach of TCS is rooted in the principle of considering a taxon concept as a name plus a description of a taxon, referring thus to the source (e.g., a published paper) where, or according to, the location of the circumscription is defined. TCS is also designed to allow representing potentially competing and conflicting classifications, and thus multiple taxonomic opinions. This goes beyond the requirements for representing the data coming from WoRMS, where a single integrated taxonomic classification and perspective is provided.

Despite the advanced problems that TCS aimed at addressing and the valuable attempt to represent taxonomic concepts in a structured and standardised manner, the uptake and adoption of TCS were and are limited, also due to its complexity, and the standard is basically considered outdated.

Figure 4: Overview of TCS2 data model (Feb 2024). Source: <https://github.com/tdwg/tcs2>

To overcome these limitations, the Taxonomic Concept Schema (TCS2) Task Group⁷ is working to create a new version of TCS⁸ as a full-fledged semantic vocabulary that defines and makes available classes and properties, together with the definition or identification of controlled vocabularies for specific properties (such as taxonomic ranks, nomenclatural status of names, etc.). As in the case of TCS, TCS2 is rooted in the distinction between taxon concepts and taxon names, as well as on the need and possibility of defining relationships between concepts and between names (in addition to relating names and concepts). Again as in TCS, a taxon concept can be identified through the combination of a label, referred to as the taxon name (not necessarily representing canonical scientific names), along with its respective source information (the *accordingTo* dimension). Although not yet finalised by the working group (as of February 2024), the diagram in Figure 4 provides a good overview of the core entities and how they are related, although potentially subject to changes as the work of the group progresses.

There is clearly a strong overlap in the requirements addressed by TCS2 and those that are being considered in the context of MAREGRAPH. TCS2 is expected to provide "the best of"

⁷ <https://www.tdwg.org/community/tnc/tcs2/>

⁸ <https://github.com/tdwg/tcs2>

taxonomic data representation, also capitalising on previous experiences and lessons learned from the development and implementation of TCS. The ongoing work of the task group is a valuable source of inspiration for the design of the ontology modules in MAREGRAPH, and we expect that it will be possible to define clear semantic alignments between our modules and the upcoming TCS2 ontology (under the assumption that an OWL ontology will be produced).

3.3 The OpenBioDiv Ontology

The OpenBioDiv Ontology (OpenBiodiv-O) [18] aims at providing classes, properties, and axioms to support knowledge representation in the domains of scholarly biodiversity publishing and biological taxonomy. As defined by its authors *“it is an ontology of the scientific process of biological taxonomy and not of any particular state of knowledge”*, thus aiming at supporting the expression of multiple scientific opinions concerning taxa, their naming and possible classifications and relationships. The OpenBioDiv Ontology is intended as the reference ontology for the Open Biodiversity Knowledge Management System⁹.

OpenBiodiv-O¹⁰ is designed to allow capturing up to a specific mention of a scientific name in a scientific article, also relying on well-established ontologies and patterns for scholarly data and bibliographic information, specifically the Semantic Publishing and Referencing Ontologies (SPAR Ontologies) [19]. When it comes to represent the taxonomic and nomenclatural perspectives, OpenBiodiv-O makes an explicit distinction between taxonomic concepts and the names used to denote them. Figure 5 provides an overview of the approach taken to represent taxonomic concepts. The figure also shows the equivalence relationship (`owl:equivalentClass`) defined between the Taxonomic Concept class and the Taxon class available in Darwin Core.

Figure 5: Taxonomic concept in OpenBiodiv-O [18]

Taxonomic concepts are then related to taxonomic names, which are then further specialised to capture the different kinds of names that can be used in relation to taxa, ranging from

⁹ OpenBiodiv, <http://openbiodiv.net/>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/vsenderov/openbiodiv-o>

vernacular names to scientific names, to fully specified taxonomic concept labels that combine a scientific name with a source where the name is used and the implied taxonomic concept is defined. The approach taken to represent scientific names is depicted in Figure 6: Taxonomic names in OpenBiodiv-O [18].

Figure 6: Taxonomic names in OpenBiodiv-O [18]

Additional specific properties, as discussed for in the previous section, are defined to allow linking taxonomic concepts and express taxonomic concept relationships that go beyond hierarchical, taxonomic parent-child relationships.

OpenBiodiv-O, as also discussed by other authors [13], ties the distinction between taxa and names to semiotics theory, and in particular to the well-known semiotic triangle, which explores the relationship between signs, objects, and interpretations. Under this view, a scientific name is a sign, symbol or label that evokes or denotes a taxonomic concept, and is used to refer to or label an observed specimen as a physical example of an organism belonging to the conceptualised taxon.

While designed to create a link between biodiversity publishing and biological taxonomy, OpenBiodiv-O includes semantically sound modelling solutions that were taken into account for the design of the ontology modules in MAREGRAPH. In addition, the ontology includes domain-specific relevant semantic alignments to other domain ontologies, such as the NOMEN ontology (a nomenclatural ontology for biological names¹¹) and the ENVO Environment Ontology¹², which were taken into account as well.

3.4 Bioschemas Taxon and TaxonName profiles

¹¹ <https://github.com/SpeciesFileGroup/nomen>

¹² <https://sites.google.com/site/environmentontology/>

Bioschemas¹³ is an initiative that extends the existing vocabulary of Schema.org to better describe resources related to life sciences. This has the goal of enabling a richer and more uniform representation of biological data across various platforms and applications, to facilitate data sharing, integration, and discovery within the life sciences community.

Bioschemas defines various “profiles”, defined as “*a community agreed layer over the Schema.org vocabulary*”, which are essentially classes (types) and sets of properties designed to describe specific entities in the life sciences domain. These profiles act as templates, providing a common framework for annotating different types of biological information.

In this context, the working group focusing on biodiversity has defined two reference profiles with classes, properties and constraint for representing taxa (Taxon profile¹⁴, based on the Taxon type) and taxon names (TaxonName profile¹⁵, based on the TaxonName type). Bioschemas profiles thus follow the knowledge representation approach already discussed for TCS and OpenBiodiv-O, where taxa and their names are treated as distinct entities. More in detail:

- a Taxon, defined as set of organisms asserted to represent a natural cohesive biological unit, can have a taxonomic rank and can be related to other taxa with parent-child relationships to induce a taxonomic classification; a Taxon can be related to taxon names with properties for denoting the currently valid/accepted name and synonyms;
- a TaxonName, defined as a name of a biological taxon, may it be valid (zoology) / accepted (botany) or not, can have a rank as well, and then relies on the existing schema.org name and author properties to allow defining the scientific name and the author.

Although not conceived as a full-fledged ontology for representing biodiversity-related information on species, Bioschemas profiles capture the heart of WoRMS data, also considering that the profiles explicitly target web portals and data registries such as GBIF and Catalogue of Life. It is also worth mentioning that, as of the release of version 13 of schema.org, the Taxon type is considered as Schema.org type with reference URI <https://schema.org/Taxon>. Considering the widespread adoption of schema.org, at least as an “annotation” vocabulary for data mark-up on web pages, it is important to recognise its role and define at least semantic alignments that allow considering the data from the “schema.org perspective”.

3.5 TAXREF-LD

TAXREF-LD [20] is a Linked Data knowledge graph representing TAXREF, the French national taxonomic register for fauna, flora, and fungi.

¹³ <https://bioschemas.org/>

¹⁴ <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/Taxon>

¹⁵ <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/TaxonName>

To provide a structured and consistent representation of taxonomic information, TAXREF-LD¹⁶ directly relies on OWL and SKOS so that OWL classes are used to represent taxa and SKOS concepts to represent scientific names. The approach for representing taxonomic and nomenclatural information is quite similar to the one that characterises Bioschemas (Franck Michel, leading author of TAXREF-LD, also co-leads the Bioschemas biodiversity group), with a distinction between taxa and names, which are related to each other.

Figure 7: Taxa and names in TAXREF-LD [20]

Figure 7 exemplifies the knowledge representation approach adopted for separating nomenclatural and from taxonomic information. Specifically:

- taxa are represented as OWL classes, and the taxonomic hierarchy is defined relying on `rdfs:subClassOf` relationships; a taxon can have a rank and is related to a reference name (the valid/accepted name) and to synonym names (if any);
- scientific names are represented as SKOS concepts, with properties to define the name and the authority.

TAXREF-LD goes beyond basic taxonomic data (scientific names, ranks, parent taxa) and covers additional aspects including vernacular names, habitat and biogeographical information, species interactions, legal and conservation statuses, cross-references to other biodiversity resources (including WoRMS) and links to media resources like photos.

The solutions adopted in TAXREF-LD are highly relevant for producing a reference ontology and Linked Open Data version of WoRMS, both from knowledge representation perspective

¹⁶ <https://github.com/frmichel/taxref-ld>

(in particular for the usage of standardised ontologies and vocabularies for representing taxonomic and nomenclatural information) and in terms of domain coverage beyond taxonomy and nomenclature (with structured and semantically rich representations for species attributes and other information).

3.6 The Marine Top Level Ontology

The Marine Top Level Ontology¹⁷ (MarineTLO), defined by the Information System Laboratory (ISL) of the Institute of Computer Science (ICS) in the Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH), is a top-level OWL ontology designed to facilitate the representation and integration of information from the marine domain.

MarineTLO provides a semantic framework for representing knowledge about marine species. It establishes a structured ontology for describing various aspects of marine life, including taxonomy, nomenclature, distribution, ecology and biological parameters.

Although the ontology is no longer actively maintained, its relevance for the marine domain is still high, also considering concrete application scenarios that were addressed relying on the ontology, such as the setup of a MarineTLO-based Warehouse integrating data from sources such as FishBase and WoRMS. As a top-level ontology, it provides reference high level concepts and properties that can be reused or extended as needed.

The relevance to our work also comes from the approach and methodology used, as the ontology was developed adopting an iterative and incremental methodology. Fully in line with our methodology, the design was driven by the identification of a set of competency questions formulated with the help of domain experts to first capture domain requirements and then evaluate the ontology.

3.7 The Catalogue Of Life Data Package specification

All existing global species databases and biodiversity information systems that act as repositories of information about various species, their distributions, habitats, ecological roles, etc. rely on data models that allow representing taxonomic classifications and nomenclature, species distributions, ecological traits, data sources and other attributes. In addition to WoRMS, well known examples include the Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS), FishBase and SeaLifeBase, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the Catalogue of Life.

As a representative example, we consider here the Catalogue of Life¹⁸ (CoL), a global species checklist and index of known species of animals, plants, fungi, and microorganisms, built by aggregating more than 100 species checklists collected from various data providers and sources. WoRMS itself is among the core data providers for CoL.

¹⁷ <https://projects.ics.forth.gr/isl/MarineTLO/>

¹⁸ <https://www.catalogueoflife.org/>

To enable the collection and integration of data, CoL relies on the so-called Catalogue of Life Data Package¹⁹ (CoLDP), a rich object-oriented domain model that defines the reference exchange format for data. The reference model allows representing taxa and scientific names as separate entities, which are then related to each other to build taxonomic classifications and define accepted names and synonyms. The model also covers relationships between taxa and between names, as well as data sources and references, vernacular names, species distribution, media objects and other attributes. While the reference data model considers taxa and scientific names as different entities, CoLDP includes a variant of the model where taxa and names, as well as taxonomic and nomenclatural attributes and properties, are merged in a single *NameUsage* entity (which resembles the Taxon class in Dwc). This allows collecting data also from data providers that do not necessarily make a distinction between taxa and names in their data models and datasets. The diagrams in the CoLDP GitHub repository help understanding the overall structure of the data model. These models are also used to “reshape” data from WoRMS and provide it to CoL.

CoLDP, although not formalised as an ontology, is quite relevant for the modelling effort done in MAREGRAPH, as it covers at least a part of the domain-specific entities and properties that characterise the data managed in WoRMS. The relevance of CoLDP, and the roots of modelling and design choices, also emerge from a recent comparison with the Taxon Concept Schema (TCS) standard (introduced before in Section 3.2), where the compatibility between the two models is discussed [21].

3.8 INSPIRE Data Specification on Species Distribution

In the European context, it is important to mention and consider the INSPIRE Data Specification on Species Distribution²⁰. This INSPIRE data specification, which focuses on the “Species Distribution” category of spatial data defined in the INSPIRE Directive, is a framework designed to facilitate the sharing and integration of data related to the distribution of species across geographical regions, in line with the overall aim of the Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE) to enable the interoperability of spatial data infrastructures within the European Union. The INSPIRE data specifications are also relevant in the context of the common European data spaces.

The specification defines data models and guidelines for the collection, management, and dissemination of data pertaining to species distribution, including information on species occurrences and habitats. The data specification covers the *“Geographical distribution of occurrence of animal and plant species aggregated by grid, region, administrative unit or other analytical unit.”*, and it will thus have a strong relevance for species occurrence data that will be considered in MAREGRAPH in relation to the EurOBIS information system and data. While a more in-depth analysis will be performed in the context of the project when focusing on EurOBIS and extending the ontology network, the INSPIRE data specification covers entities that have relevance when representing and describing species. In the data model, distribution information is linked to species names denoting the species for which the

¹⁹ <https://github.com/CatalogueOfLife/coldp>

²⁰ https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/publications/inspire-data-specification-species-distribution-technical-guidelines_en

information is collected and provided. Species names refer to species through a unique identifier, which should be taken from one of three recognised European Classification systems and classification schemes for species, namely EU-Nomen²¹ (the preferred reference list), EUNIS and Natura2000. Additional attributes allow defining and referencing the scientific name (with authority info) used in a national nomenclature database of the data-providing country, as well as the reference scheme where the local taxonomic concept is defined. The local taxonomic concept can then be related to the concept defined by the reference species classification scheme (i.e., EU-Nomen, EUNIS or Natura2000).

It is worth highlighting that the infrastructure that supports the EU-Nomen portal and the corresponding Pan-European Species directory Infrastructure (PESI) – considered as the preferred reference list for species in the INSPIRE specification, as mentioned before – is basically the Aphia database that powers WoRMS, in the form of the European Register of Marine Species (ERMS). There is thus a full compatibility between the possibility to shape species occurrence data according to the INSPIRE data specification and the need to reference marine species as represented in WoRMS.

²¹ <http://www.eu-nomen.eu/portal/>

4 Requirements collection

During the first year of the project, we collected requirements for guiding the creation of the ontologies.

The requirements have been gathered during different phases of the methodology:

- internal interactions with the WoRMS domain experts. In this case, specific requests of data representation and data exports were provided to the modellers to better understand the data to be represented with the ontologies;
- public interactions with people from the community who participated in the various workshops; in particular, the first business workshop in which the topics addressed by MAREGRAPH were presented, the first and second thematic workshops on WoRMS, in which the ontologies for WoRMS in their initial versions were discussed and presented.

We identify three types of different requirements that guided the ontology modules design and development:

1. *user cases*;
2. *competency questions*;
3. *data details* coming directly from the database.

In the following subsection we present the different types of requirements we considered to produce the network of ontology (see Section 5).

4.1 Use cases

During the first business workshop we asked stakeholders to identify use cases of interest to them for all possible datasets of the MAREGRAPH project. With the term use case we mean a specific situation of data exchange for which ontologies can be used.

We classified the use cases listed and discussed during the workshops; in Table 3 we report those that are most closely related to the data contained in WoRMS, the object of analysis for the ontologies of this deliverable.

In Table 3 words are in bold to highlight important entities of the domain to be modelled, not only for WoRMS (e.g., species distribution) but in general for the project (e.g., species occurrences).

Table 3: Use case definition during workshops with external stakeholders

<i>Use Case ID</i>	<i>Use Case description</i>
US1	I would like to have use cases which can help users to integrate data about distribution, occurrences and functional traits of marine species
US2	To be able to follow translation path-ways between scientific taxonomic references and common or commercial language names for marine species
US3	The ability to query the graph using semantics that I'm used to (e.g., generic semantic conventions like schema.org or research-focused standards like DCAT)

US4	To enable tracking how the taxonomic reference changed over time and how that affects the interpretation of data published at those specific times
US5	To enable publishing datapoints and datasets linked to up the reference marine-regions and marine-species (and sub elements of their setup: place types, geographic relations, traits, ...)
US6	I want to be able to obtain the most up-to-date taxonomic information for marine species

Specific mention should be made for US4, which requires the ability to track changes in taxonomic information for marine species over time. At present, there is no specific ontology design pattern related to time-indexed situations that has been implemented in the ontology network due to the lack of this type of data in the WoRMS database. However, evolutions in scientific names and taxonomic classification can be produced in the linked open data according to the so-called taxon name ontology module we have developed (see Section 5.2).

4.2 Competency questions

Competency questions are important building blocks of the eXtreme Design methodology we have followed so far when designing and engineering the ontologies.

Competency questions can be defined as questions posed by users (user centricity), expressed in natural language, whose answers can be obtained by leveraging the capabilities of the ontologies to support those questions.

In the context of ontology design, competency questions play a crucial role in guiding the development and evaluation of the ontology. They serve several purposes:

- *Requirements Elicitation*: Competency questions help identify the key information needs and requirements of users or stakeholders. By articulating the questions users want to ask of the ontology, designers can ensure that the ontology addresses relevant aspects of the domain.
- *Scope Definition*: Competency questions help define the scope and boundaries of the ontology. They clarify what aspects of the domain the ontology should cover and what types of information it should represent.
- *Evaluation Criteria*: Competency questions serve as criteria for evaluating the ontology's effectiveness and completeness. If the ontology can accurately and comprehensively answer the competency questions, it indicates that the ontology adequately represents the domain.
- *Quality Assurance*: Competency questions help assess the quality of the ontology's design and implementation. By verifying that the ontology can answer the intended questions correctly, designers can ensure its accuracy, consistency, and relevance.
- *Iterative Improvement*: Competency questions facilitate iterative refinement and enhancement of the ontology. As new requirements emerge or existing ones change, designers can modify the ontology and evaluate its effectiveness based on the evolving set of competency questions.

Overall, competency questions act as a bridge between the conceptualization of a domain and the development of an ontology, guiding designers in creating ontologies that accurately capture the knowledge and meet the information needs of users.

As for use cases, during the first business workshop we asked participants to formulate questions of their interest, providing some examples already outlined by VLIZ's domain experts in preparation of the meeting.

Table 4 lists some competency questions that have been identified for the WoRMS data.

Table 4: Competency definition during workshops with external and internal stakeholders

Competency question ID	Competency question description
CQ1	Where does species XX appear?
CQ2	Which species from the Habitat/Bird Directive are on the IUCN Red List?
CQ3	Can I surf in the area ZZ? Are there sharks?
CQ4	Which alien species are known to occur in the Mediterranean Sea?
CQ5	Which is the body size of species XX?
CQ6	Who are the owners of the images associated with species XX?
CQ7	What are the synonyms for the name YY?
CQ8	Which is the aphia identifier for species XX?
CQ9	Which are the common names in Italian for species XX?
CQ10	Which are all the attributes and traits for species XX with the related sources?
CQ11	What are the habitats of species XX?
CQ12	Which species are known to be invasive in region ZZ?
CQ13	Which species have been discovered in region ZZ?
CQ14	What is the type locality of species XX?
CQ15	What is the taxonomic classification (e.g., kingdom, phylum, class) of species XX?
CQ16	What is the valid/accepted scientific name for species XX?
CQ17	What is the conservation status of species XX according to IUCN?
CQ18	What are the references/sources cited for the taxonomic information of species XX?

4.3 WoRMS Data Details

The main types of data managed by WoRMS are the following:

- Taxonomies;
- Distributions;
- Attributes and Traits;
- Specimen (very few and to be further investigated in the future)
- Vernacular names
- Identifiers
- Notes
- Sources

- Images

Table 5 includes the main aspects regarding the WoRMS data that were presented by VLIZ's colleagues during the first thematic workshop on WoRMS. This provides us with a list of possible types of data to be taken into account in a more bottom-up approach when designing ontology modules of the APHIA network.

Table 5: Data aspects to be considered for producing Linked Open Data and developing ontologies

Aspect ID	Aspect description	Remarks
AS1	basics of id, name	Worms does not track taxa but only names. Names are associated with a URN identifier
AS2	resource metadata (license, creator, ...)	-
AS3	taxonomic status	Controlled vocabulary to be considered
AS4	parent by id (taxonomic hierarchy)	-
AS5	names on all levels of the taxonomic tree	-
AS6	geographic distribution	Link to marine regions
AS7	vernacular (alternative names)	Available translated variants Challenge: attribute the association with the authoritative "source"
AS8	source	Link to the authoritative source
AS9	traits / attributes	Secondary reference requires concepts
AS10	media (image/video)	-
AS11	links (other sources)	-
AS12	notes	Free text field. Note types are available
AS13	specimens	Very limited

5 Preliminary ontology design – the APHIA network

On the basis of the previously described methodology, we designed and developed a preliminary set of ontology modules that are all connected with other each, thus forming a network of modules named APHIA network.

A top-level ontology is used to realise the network, enabling the linking between the different modules and semantic inference.

The modules are dependent on the different types of data that the WoRMS database provides to its users. In particular, the current APHIA network consists of four domain ontology modules in addition to the top-level ontology. The modules are depicted in Figure 8. The grey circles represent our developed ontologies, the white circles are external ontologies we import whilst the light blue circle is the marine region ontology already published by VLIZ. The arrows in Figure 8. represent `owl:imports` axioms among the ontologies or the re-use (`uses` property) of single elements of other modules/ontologies. In Figure 8 there are also the prefixes of each module or ontology illustrated.

Figure 8: The APHIA network of ontologies

All the ontologies, and their elements, are identified by URIs that have been formed according to the various European and national best practices²². Specifically, the URIs are built according to the following scheme:

```
https://[namespace]/[type]/[concept]/[reference]
```

As shown in Figure 8 in the prefixes box, the chosen namespace is `aphia.org`. Since we are defining URIs for ontologies, the type chosen is `ns`, following Digital Flanders rules and W3C practice²³. The concept represents the name of the ontology and the reference part is the unique identifier of each element of the ontology.

The network's domain ontologies include labels and definitions available in English and Italian, thus enabling multilingualism. In this preliminary version of the network, only one of the ontologies, in addition to English and Italian, also includes labels and definitions in Dutch. We plan to add the Dutch version of all labels and definitions for all ontologies in the coming months, to include them in the final version of the ontologies.

In addition, OWL restrictions; namely, special kinds of class descriptions have been introduced in all the modules. These are anonymous classes, i.e., classes of all individuals that satisfy the specific restrictions (constraints on values and properties). The OWL restrictions allow us to enable semantic inference and provide a view of cardinality constraints that impact on the data quality.

All the ontologies are currently publicly available in the following github repository <https://github.com/MareGraph-EU/assets/tree/main> where the produced versions are tracked.

The publication on github is the result of a long internal discussion with the WoRMS database domain experts. We have yet to open the public review of the ontologies and plan to fulfil this phase of the overall methodology identified in WP2 after the submission of this deliverable. This choice is motivated to the need to find a general internal agreement on the core design of each ontology module before opening up to the general public.

In the following subsections we describe each module, highlighting some design choices and semantic alignments to external ontologies, if available.

5.1 Top-level ontology module

As previously introduced, in order to connect all the domain ontology modules of the APHIA network, and also define general entities that are independent of the specific fishery domain (e.g., a source, a value, a name) but useful for our modelling needs, we decided to propose the definition of a so-called top-level ontology.

The ontology imports a well-known foundational ontology available in the ontology representation literature; namely, `d0` that in turn imports the DOLCE+DnS Ultralite ontology,

²² <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre/document/10-rules-persistent-uris>

²³ The Italian government generally uses the same scheme to specify URIs; however, the 'type' element chosen is 'onto' when identifying ontologies, in order to have URIs that are as spoken as possible

a simplification of some parts of the DOLCE Lite-Plus library [1] D0 defines general classes like `Characteristic` represented as the union of other classes expressed in DOLCE+DnS Ultralite ontology.

When importing an entire ontology, the imported ontology is an integral part of the ontological definition being made. In the specific case of the top-level various classes and properties of d0 and thus DOLCE + DnS Ultralite were then used directly or indirectly in the domain ontology modules of the APHIA network described below.

However, for general modelling needs, further classes and properties were added. In particular, we the classes `top-level:Name`, `top-level:Source`, `top-level:Value`, `top-level:UnitOfMeasure`, `top-level:Identifier`, `top-level:IdentifierType`, `top-level:System` and their related object and data type properties (e.g., `top-level:hasIdentifier`, `top-level:isAssignedBy`, `top-level:hasType`, `top-level:value`, `top-level:hasValue`).

5.2 Taxon name ontology module

One of the most important domain ontology modules of the APHIA network is the so-called Taxon name module (preferred prefix `taxon-name`).

During the last year of the project, this module was discussed extensively with the WoRMS database domain experts because it includes critical modelling elements that are necessary to provide consistent semantics. Moreover, this module is the basis for all the other modules described in this deliverable and probably for all the other ontologies that will be developed in the context of the MAREGRAPH project. In fact, it represents the set of taxonomic information that allows for the unambiguous identification of marine species and any changes in classification that occur over time.

In Figure 9 and Figure 10 we illustrate two graphical representations expressed using the Graffoo notation of two main elements of the ontology; namely, the scientific names and all the taxonomic information and the vernacular names, respectively.

Figure 9: The scientific name and other taxonomic information of the Taxon name ontology module

Figure 10: The vernacular name of the Taxon name ontology module

As reported earlier, the problem of identifying marine species by their names has been widely discussed in the literature. In the WoRMS database, all information on marine species is linked to scientific names because in the relevant publications, from which WoRMS derives its data, only the names are cited to identify the species (set of organisms) that are thus implied. This certainly simplifies database management, but from a semantic point of view, such management creates semantic inconsistencies.

In general, looking at the reality of the domain, the semiotic triangle applies: taxa are things (i.e., referents) to which our concepts (i.e., references) refer and are labelled or symbolised by means of scientific names (see Section 3). This suggests that there should be a clear distinction between things and the symbols used to label them. For example, a picture of a fish represents an organism (a thing), not the name of that organism; therefore, it cannot simply be associated with a scientific name, even though that name is used to refer to the organism.

In the light of these considerations, we propose an ontology module where there exist two classes: a `taxon-name:Taxon` class (concept) that is distinct from the class `taxon-name:TaxonName` that represents the name (symbol, label). Using a class to represent the name of the taxon then allows us to predicate on that name to specify for instance the authorship (`taxon-name:authorship` in Figure 9), the status (`taxon-name:Status` in Figure 9) or other properties. This modelling choice is the same as the one adopted in several semantic-based scientific publications and, specifically, the one proposed by an extension of the well-consolidated SKOS ontology named SKOS-XL (as also represented in Figure 9). In SKOS-XL the Label is a class (`taxon-name:TaxonName rdfs:subClassOf skos-xl:Label`) and the concept is the class from SKOS (`taxon-name:Taxon rdfs:subClassOf skos:Concept`).

Since a taxon may have different types of names other than the scientific one, we introduced in the top-level ontology module a generic abstract class `top-level:Name` that groups all these different types. This modelling choice allows for specifying general properties that may apply to all types of names (i.e., the `taxon-name:denotes` object property that links `top-level:Name` to `taxon-name:Taxon`) In fact, `top-level:Name` is the super class of both `taxon-name:TaxonName` and `taxon-name:VernacularName` (see Figure 10) where the specialisations are marked as disjoint (Figure 10) because if the name is a scientific name it cannot be at the same time a vernacular name. This latter is an informal name used by the general public or within specific communities to refer to an organism. Unlike scientific names, which follow standardised rules, vernacular names can vary regionally or culturally. These names often reflect characteristics, behaviours, appearances, or uses of the organism and can be quite diverse across different languages and regions. These two latter elements are in fact used to characterise the semantic definition of vernacular names and are represented using two properties, `dct:language` and `dct:coverage` in Figure 10.

In addition to the above important modelling part of the ontology, it represents other taxonomic data like the whole taxonomic classification of taxa (through the `taxon-name:Rank` class), any identifier, including the APHIA identifier (i.e., the identifier assigned by the APHIA system – `taxon-name:aphiaID` in Figure 9), associated with the name since in WoRMS this information is pertinent to the scientific name of the species, the relations between the taxon and its name depending on the status of the name (e.g., accepted, unaccepted) – `taxon-name:hasAcceptedName` `taxon-name:hasSynonymName` in Figure 9.

Finally, for all key classes of this ontology module `taxon-name:Taxon`, `taxon-name:TaxonName`, `taxon-name:VernacularName` the (scientific) source is captured in order to always maintain the provenance of the information included in scientific publications.

5.2.1 Implemented ontology design patterns

This ontology module implements, in the reference domain, a set of general ontology design patterns. The patterns are listed in Table 6 along with the related implementation in the taxon name ontology module.

Table 6: Ontology Design Patterns implemented in the Taxon name ontology module

<i>Name of the ontology design pattern</i>	<i>Taxon name module element</i>
Classification ²⁴	taxon-nameTaxonName top-level:hasStatus taxon-name:Status taxon-name:TaxonName taxon-name:isOfRank taxon-name:Rank
LinnaeanTaxonomy (only partially) ²⁵	taxon-name:Taxon, taxon-name:hasChild, taxon-name:hasParent
Literal Reification ²⁶	taxon-name:TaxonName taxon-name:scientificName rdfs:Literal

5.2.2 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

We introduced preliminary direct and indirect semantic alignments with external ontologies.

In particular, all classes are aligned with the top-level ontology and thus to DUL/d0 foundational ontology. Moreover, using the PROV-O Web standard, we introduced some lightweight semantic alignments indicating that certain defined classes in the taxon name ontology module are derived from other available ontologies of the domain.

One of the external reference vocabularies for this module is Darwin Core (see Section 3). However, it is worth noting that although the RDF version is mentioned in the documentation, there does not seem to be a specific RDF vocabulary for Darwin Core. There is only a guideline on how to represent linked data with the vocabulary. Despite of this uncertain scenario, URIs for properties and classes are specified in the vocabulary as if describing a real RDF vocabulary; therefore, those URIs have been used to provide semantic alignments however specifically required by VLIZ.

Table 7: Semantic alignments for the Taxon name ontology module

<i>Taxon name module element</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment</i>	<i>External ontology</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment type</i>
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²⁴ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Classification>

²⁵ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:LinnaeanTaxonomy>

²⁶ http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Literal_Reification

taxon-name:Taxon	subClassOf dul:Concept subClassOf skos:Concept prov:wasDerivedFrom dwc:Taxon prov:wasDerivedFrom schema:Taxon	DUL Foundational ontology SKOS ontology Darwin Core Vocabulary Schema.org vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:TaxonName	subClassOf skos-xl:Label prov:wasDerivedFrom openbiodiv:LatinName prov:wasDerivedFrom bioschemas:TaxonName	SKOS-XL ontology OpenBiodiv-O ontology Bioschemas.org	indirect
taxon-name:VernacularName	prov:wasDerivedFrom opebiodiv:VernacularName	OpenBiodiv-O ontology	indirect
taxon-name:Status	subClassOf skos:Concept subClassOf dul:Concept	SKOS ontology DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
taxon-name:Rank	subClassOf skos:Concept subClassOf dul:Concept	SKOS ontology DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
taxon-name:UnacceptedReason	subClassOf skos:Concept subClassOf dul:Concept	SKOS ontology DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
dct:LinguisticSystem	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:Location	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:source	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:coverage	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:language	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
taxon-name:hasChild	skos:narrower	SKOS ontology	indirect
taxon-name:hasParent	skos:broader	SKOS ontology	indirect
taxon-name:aphiaID	dwc:scientificNameID	Darwin Core vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:authorship	dwc:scientificNameAuthorship	Darwin Core vocabulary	indirect

taxon-name:fullScientificName	dwc:scientificName skos-xl:literalForm	Darwin Core vocabulary SKOS-XL vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:scientificName	skos-xl:literalForm	SKOS-XL vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:vernacularName	dwc:vernacularName skos-xl:literalForm	Darwin Core vocabulary SKOS-XL vocabulary	indirect

All the other object properties are aligned with the top-level ontology and thus to DUL/d0 foundational ontologies.

5.3 Distribution ontology module

The distribution ontology (preferred prefix: `td`) module has been developed to represent all the geographical elements that allow one to localise the marine species in marine regions, providing context information for the species with respect to their locations.

The graphical representation using the Graffoo notation is illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: The Distribution ontology module

From the proposed modelling, we observe that a `taxon-name:Taxon` can be directed linked to a marine region (`mr:MRGeoObject`). This latter class of the ontology is defined within the related Marine Regions Gazetteer ontology, which was already available before the official start of the MAREGRAPH project. However, during the design of the distribution module we noticed the lack of the definition of the property `mr:occursIn` within the ontology source code, despite its description was present in related documentation. This discrepancy will bring us to modify the Marine Regions Gazetteer ontology in the context of

the MAREGRAPH project, to reflect the presence of this important property required for defining the distribution.

In addition to the direct link to a Marine Region, the ontology includes the representation of a general concept of Distribution (the class `td:Distribution` in Figure 11) that is an overall situation that puts together many elements that characterise the geographical distribution of marine species. In essence, from a technical point of view, it represents an n-ary relationship.

In particular, based on WoRMS data, the distribution defines not only the area (the `td:hasArea` object property of Figure 11 that connects to a Marine Region) but also the geometry (`locn:Geometry`), the origin of the species (the `td:Origin` class), the invasiveness information (the `td:Invasiveness` class); that is, the propensity of an introduced species to invade a recipient ecosystem, the type of occurrence (the `td:Occurrence` class); that is, the presence of species at locations of interest, the (scientific) source (the `top-level:Source` class) from which all the distribution details are derived, whether it is typed (the `td:isTypeLocality` data type property) or not and any other note (the `skos:note` data type property), written in the form of a string, for describing the distribution.

It is important to notice that most of the classes connected to the Distribution class can be modelled as controlled vocabularies; that is, the individuals of all those classes can be the concepts of SKOS-based controlled vocabularies to be built according to the terminology provided by the marine specie website (<https://www.marinespecies.org/introduced/terminology.php>).

5.3.1 Implemented ontology design patterns

The main ontology design patterns that has been used in this ontology module are the situation pattern²⁷, that has been implemented through the class `td:Distribution` for the `taxon-name:Taxon`, and the place pattern²⁸ that is implemented through the properties `mr:occursIn` and `td:hasArea` that link the taxon and its distribution, respectively, to a place.

5.3.2 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

The design of the distribution module is characterised by preliminary identified direct and indirect semantic alignments to external ontologies. The following Table 8 lists those alignments.

Table 8: Semantic alignments for the Distribution ontology module

²⁷ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Situation>

²⁸ <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/cp/owl/place.owl>

Distribution module element	Semantic Alignment	External ontology	Semantic Alignment type
td:Distribution	subClassOf dul:Situation	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
td:Origin	subClassOf dul:Concept subClassOf skos:Concept	DUL Foundational ontology SKOS ontology	indirect
td:Invasiveness	subClassOf dul:Concept subClassOf skos:Concept	DUL Foundational ontology SKOS ontology	indirect
td:Occurrence	subClassOf dul:Concept subClassOf skos:Concept	DUL Foundational ontology SKOS ontology	indirect
locn:geometry	-	Core Location vocabulary	direct
skos:note	-	SKOS ontology	direct
dct:source	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
td:hasArea	subPropertyOf dwc:locality subPropertyOf dul:hasLocation	Darwin Core vocabulary DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
td:hasOccurrence	subPropertyOf dwc:occurrenceStatus subPropertyOf dul:isAssociatedWith	Darwin Core vocabulary DUL Foundational ontology	indirect

All the rest of the object properties are aligned with the DUL foundational ontology used in the top-level ontology module of the APHIA network.

5.4 Media ontology module

The media ontology (preferred prefix: `media`) module has been developed to represent all the media resources (e.g., video, image) that can be associated with marine species.

The graphical representation using the Graffoo notation is illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12: The Media ontology module

For this ontology we also produced the UML diagram, according to our methodology. The UML class diagram, with the indication of the cardinalities of the properties, is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: UML diagram for the media ontology module

We plan to produce all UML diagrams for all other ontology modules in the coming months, so that we will have them available for the publication of the final version of all ontologies.

In general, the media module follows the modelling pattern that has been proposed in schema.org. Therefore, the `taxon-name:Taxon` is the subject (the

`media:isSubjectOf` object property) of a generic media object (the abstract class `media:MediaObject` in Figure 12 and Figure 13). The object can be instantiated with two types named `media:ImageObject` and `media:VideoObject` representing images and videos resources, respectively. Note that these two classes are defined as disjoint, meaning that instances of type `media:ImageObject` cannot be at the same time instances of `media:VideoObject`. The proposed modelling is sufficiently general to accommodate the introduction in the future of other types of media objects like audio for instance.

For describing those types of objects a set of properties of the `media:MediaObject` class has been identified in order to represent:

- the format of the media object (the object property `dct:format` connected to the class `dct:MediaTypeObject`);
- the license associated with the media object (the object property `dct:license` connected to the class `dct:LisenceDocument`);
- the title and description if available of the media object (`dct:title` and `dct:description` data type properties);
- the person or organization (i.e., agents) that owns rights on the media object (`dct:rightsholder` connected to the class `dct:Agent`)

The properties included in the graphical representation of the module are the most recurrent and important ones. Additional properties can be specified in the data when required (e.g., size, URL of the media resource) thanks to the semantic alignment of the `media:MediaObject` class to the related Schema.org class (see Section 5.4.1). To this end, it is worth pointing out that, following other European practices, we have decided to indirectly align our ontological module with Schema.org in order to be partially independent of that model, thus guaranteeing a certain degree of sustainability of our semantic definition over time. Schema.org is a data model proposed by a private US company that could decide, at any time, to discontinue maintenance of the model or modify currently defined elements according to its own specific market needs. However, despite these motivations for indirect alignment, this modelling choice allows us to use Schema.org in the LOD anyway, borrowing certain properties from it only when necessary, according to data representation needs.

In contrast, this module uses directly many properties of Dublin Core. Dublin Core is an ISO standard whose definition follows a typically long standardization programme. This guarantees the stability of the model over time, and in turn the sustainability of our semantics that directly reuse it.

5.4.1 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

The following Table 9 lists the preliminary semantic alignments of the media ontology module.

Table 9: Semantic alignments for the Media module

Media module element	Semantic Alignment	External ontology	Semantic Alignment type
media:MediaObject	subClassOf schema:MediaObject	Schema.org vocabulary	indirect
media:ImageObject	subClassOf schema:ImageObject	Schema.org vocabulary	indirect
media:VideoObject	subClassOf schema:VideoObject	Schema.org vocabulary	indirect
dct:Agent	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:LicenseDocument	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:MediaTypeOrExtent	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:rightsHolder dct:title dct:description dct:license dct:format dct:subject	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct

5.5 Attribute and trait ontology module

The attribute and trait ontology (preferred prefix: `tat`) module has been developed to represent all the data regarding attributes and traits of marine species and their context information, which may not even be known a priori and extended in the future.

Attributes are qualities or characteristics whereby a taxon can be distinguished and are typically associated with categorial values. In contrast, traits are any measurable or observable characteristics of an organism. In the WoRMS database, at the time being, there is only one documented trait for marine species; that is, the 'body size'.

The graphical representation using the Graffoo notation of the ontology module is illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14: The Attribute-trait ontology module

In the proposed modelling despite the environment is considered an attribute of a taxon, it has been modelled in a different way with respect to other attributes/traits. In fact, the habitat or environment is an important element that has its own standalone identity in many vocabularies available in the literature. Therefore, it has been decided to make it evident in the modelling through the definition of a class named `taxon:Environment` which is linked to the taxon through the object property `taxon:hasHabitat`, a terminology widely recognised in the fishery domain. The individuals of the `taxon:Environment` class can be the concepts of a specific SKOS-based controlled vocabulary to be created to represent the different habitats of the marine species (e.g., marine, freshwater).

The rest of the attributes and traits included in the WoRMS database were modelled with a highly flexible modelling scheme to accommodate future evolutions on the management and content of this type of data in the WoRMS system. In essence, the proposed modelling allows one to introduce additional traits and attributes, and further extra context information for them, without repeatedly changing the ontology with each new evolution/extension.

Since, the attributes and traits are used to *describe* the qualities and characteristics of a taxon, we introduced the class `taxon:TaxonDescription` for this purpose. As in the case of the Distribution class in the distribution ontology module, the `taxon:TaxonDescription` is a situation description that allows one to put together, for a given `taxon-name:Taxon`, different elements:

1. the trait or attribute itself (the class `taxon:TaxonCharacteristic` then specialised in `taxon:Trait` and `taxon:Attribute` classes in Figure 14);
2. the value the attribute or trait assumes (the class `top-level:Value`), be it categorial or quantitative value (in the latter case a `top-level:UnitOfMeasure` is specified);
3. an extra specification (the class `taxon:SpecificationContext`) that combines additional parameters (`dul:Parameter`), and their values (the class `top-level:Value`) to connote the attributes and traits of the taxon description (examples of specification contexts are: sex, life stage and their permitted values);

4. the (scientific) source (the class `top-level:Source` in Figure 14) from which the data regarding the qualities and characteristics of a taxon was derived.

In domain literature, attributes and traits are well-identified in thesauri (e.g., <https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/ontologies/ZOOPLANKTRAITS>) or, in general, in controlled vocabularies of the fishery domain. To this end, it is notable the high interest of some people of the MAREGRAPH co-creation programme, working in the context of the LifeWatch project, to create together with the partners of the project consortium a more comprehensive controlled vocabulary on trait/attribute also using the data coming from the WoRMS database. To achieve this objective, in the ontology we specified a strong semantic alignment towards concepts of these thesauri (see Section 5.5.2). In general, the individuals of the classes `tat:Attribute`, `tat:Trait` and `tat:Environment` can be used to create SKOS-based controlled vocabularies based on the data used in WoRMS.

5.5.1 Implemented ontology design patterns

This ontology module implements, in the reference domain, a set of general ontology design patterns. The patterns are listed in Table 10 along with the related implementation in the attribute-trait ontology module.

Table 10: Ontology Design Patterns implemented in the Attribute-trait ontology module

<i>Name of the ontology design pattern</i>	<i>Attribute-trait module element</i>
Classification ²⁹	<code>tat:TaxonCharacteristic top-level:hasType top-level:Type</code>
Description ³⁰	<code>tat:TaxonDescription</code>
Species Habitat ³¹	<code>taxon-name:Taxon tat:hasHabitat tat:Environment</code>
Region ³²	<code>tat:TaxonDescription top-level:hasValue top-level:Value</code>

5.5.2 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

As in the other ontology modules, we introduced preliminary direct and indirect semantic alignments with external ontologies. Specifically, all the main classes of the module, as illustrated in Figure 14, are aligned with the top-level ontology that in turn directly reuses DUL Foundation ontology (for example, the class `TaxonDescription` is `subClassOf`

²⁹ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Classification>

³⁰ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Description>

³¹ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:SpeciesHabitat>

³² <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Region>

`dul:Description`). In the specific case of parameters of the specification context entity we introduced, we reuse directly the class `dul:Parameter` defined in DUL.

In terms of properties, all object properties are aligned with the properties of the top-level ontology, directly reusing the object properties of DUL. The only exceptions are the source from which we derive taxon trait and attribute data and the additional notes, modelled as strings, used to enrich the description of taxon traits/attributes. In these cases, we directly re-use the `dct:source` property of the ISO Dublin Core standard and `skos:note` of the SKOS ontology Web standard, respectively, as was done in the previously described ontology modules of the APHIA network.

Each single alignment currently included in the ontology module is listed in the following Table 11.

Table 11: Semantic alignments for Attribute-trait ontology module

Attribute-trait module element	Semantic Alignment	External ontology	Semantic Alignment type
<code>tat:TaxonDescription</code>	<code>subClassOf dul:Description</code>	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
<code>tat:TaxonCharacteristic</code>	<code>subClassOf dul:Characteristic</code>	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
<code>tat:SpecificationContext</code>	<code>subClassOf dul:Description</code>	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
<code>tat:Environment</code>	<code>subClassOf skos:Concept</code> <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_01000739></code>	SKOS ontology ENVO ontology (OBO foundry)	indirect
<code>tat:Attribute</code>	<code>subClassOf skos:Concept</code>	SKOS ontology	indirect
<code>tat:Trait</code>	<code>subClassOf skos:Concept</code> <code>equivalentClass <https://kos.lifewatch.eu/thesauri/fishtraits/c_4></code>	SKOS ontology LifeWatch Fish Traits Thesaurus	indirect
<code>dul:Parameter</code>	-	DUL Foundational ontology	direct
<code>skos:note</code>	-	SKOS ontology	direct
<code>dct:source</code>	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
<code>tat:definesParameter</code>	<code>dul:defines</code>	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect

tat: hasAdditionalDescription	dul:isDescribedBy	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
tat: hasExtraSpecification	dul:isRelatedToDescription	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
tat: hasTaxonCharacteristic	dul:defines	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
tat:hasHabitat	dul:isAssociatedWith	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect

6 How to use the ontologies with real data: small examples

In order to highlight possible critical paths in the creation of LOD using the ontologies previously discussed, we tried to produce so-called reference examples on how to apply the ontologies to real data from WoRMS.

The most critical element is represented by the URI for the Taxon concept. Although from a semantic point of view, the distinction between Taxon and Taxon Name is fundamental to guarantee a certain degree of semantic integrity and consistency, and offered in all existing semantic data models of the reference literature, how to identify a Taxon seems still a challenging task. In the domain, in fact it is not easy to assign a unique identifier for the Taxon (a set of organisms), due to a lack of common agreement on that identification among domain scientists.

A possible solution is to use blank nodes that are nested within the Taxon Name entity to which the APHIA identifier can be assigned and used for creating URIs of the Taxon Name entities.

Blank nodes in general are discouraged in the Linked Open Data world, where the first rule is to provide URIs for everything of the domain being described³³. Blank nodes can in fact introduce issues in the data querying and management [9]. Despite these observations, we reached an internal consensus to use them in the data as the only solution to face a generalised problem still undefined regarding how to identify Taxon.

In this section we provide a few examples on the reference implementation dataset that we produced from WoRMS data, and that can be used to guide the overall LOD transformation process as described in WP5.

Figure 15 illustrates the example of use of the Taxon Name ontology module to describe the marine species *Scophthalmus maximus*.

³³ <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

```

# Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758) - Accepted
<https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/127149> a taxon-name:TaxonName , skos-xl:Label ;
  rdfs:label "Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  taxon-name:aphiaID "127149" ;
  dwc:scientificNameID "127149" ;
  taxon-name:scientificName "Scophthalmus maximus" ;
  taxon-name:authorship "(Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  dwc:scientificNameAuthorship "(Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  taxon-name:fullScientificName "Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  skos-xl:literalForm "Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  dwc:scientificName "Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  taxon-name:hasStatus <https://aphia.org/id/taxonomic-status/accepted> ;
  taxon-name:isOfRank <https://aphia.org/id/rank/species> ;
  foaf:depiction <https://images.marinespecies.org/thumbs/3558_scophthalmus-maximus-linnaeus-1758.jpg?w=700.> ;
  dwc:taxonRank <https://aphia.org/id/rank/species> ;
  dct:source <https://www.doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.542> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/publication/260563> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/publication/98466> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/publication/61331> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/publication/70441> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/dataset/17> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/dataset/42> ,
    <https://www.doi.org/10.1111/raq.12052> ,
    <https://www.doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02745-4> ;
  taxon-name:hasSynonym <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/1544773> ;
  taxon-name:denotes _:b0 ;
  top-level:hasIdentifier <https://aphia.org/id/identifier/fishbase-1348> ;
  rdfs:seeAlso <http://www.fishbase.org/Summary/SpeciesSummary.php?id=1348> ,
    <http://apiv3.iucnredlist.org/api/v3/taxonredirect/198731> ,
    <http://www.itis.gov/servlet/SingleRpt/SingleRpt?search_topic=TSN&search_value=172748> ,
    <https://www.boldsystems.org/index.php/Taxbrowser_Taxonpage?taxid=78405> .

```

Figure 15: Example of use of Taxon Name ontology module and its semantic alignments with real data

In Figure 15 there is an instance of the Taxon Name entity, whose URI follows the policy described in Section 5 and the APHIA identifier is used as the reference part of the URI³⁴.

In the example above, we also materialise the semantic alignments to SKOS-XL ontology, we import and extend, and to the Darwin Core model through properties like `dwc:scientificName`, `dwc:scientificNameID`, etc.

As it can be noticed, the property `taxon-name:denotes` points to something identified by `_:b0` which is a convention to refer to blank nodes. That property links the Taxon Name with the Taxon entity, this latter defined in Figure 16.

³⁴ We remind here that WoRMS is a database of only names; therefore, it is structured so that all the information is attached to names.

```

_:b0 a taxon-name:Taxon , skos:Concept ;
taxon-name:hasAcceptedName <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/127149> ;
tat:hasHabitat <https://aphia.org/id/environment/marine> ,
..... <https://aphia.org/id/environment/brackish> ;
taxon-name:hasSynonymName <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/1544773> ;
media:isSubjectOf <https://aphia.org/id/image/3558> ;
td:hasDistribution <https://aphia.org/id/distribution/1431356> ;
taxon-name:isDenotedBy <https://aphia.org/id/vernacular-name/3136> ,
..... <https://aphia.org/id/vernacular-name/14224> ;
skos:closeMatch <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q217329> ;
taxon-name:hasParent _:b1 .

_:b1 a taxon-name:Taxon , skos:Concept ;
..... taxon-name:hasAcceptedName <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/126124> .

```

Figure 16: Taxon materialisation using the Taxon Name and other ontology modules

In Figure 16 we define a blank node that is a `taxon-name:Taxon` that has its `acceptedName` linked to the URI presented in Figure 15 and a set of other information that is connected with the Taxon concept. In particular, the example illustrates how to specify an attribute, which is the habitat or environment, vernacular names and the distribution, this latter represented in RDF and depicted in Figure 17.

Please note that in order to create the taxonomic hierarchy between Taxon we use the `taxon-name:hasParent` property that in turn links to another blank node `_:b1` representing another taxon (as shown in Figure 16) with its own accepted name.

Finally, Figure 17 depicts the materialisation of the distribution of the marine species *Scophthalmus maximus*.

```

<https://aphia.org/id/distribution/1431356> a td:Distribution ;
  rdfs:label "Distribution for Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758) – Chinese part of the Yellow Sea"@en ;
  td:isDistributionOf [
    a taxon-name:Taxon , skos:Concept ;
    taxon-name:isDenotedBy <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/127149> .
  ] ;
  td:hasArea <http://marineregions.org/mrgid/25469> ;
  dwc:locality <http://marineregions.org/mrgid/25469> ;
  td:hasOrigin <https://aphia.org/id/origin/alien> ;
  td:hasInvasiveness <https://aphia.org/id/invasiveness/not-specified> ;
  td:hasOccurrence <https://aphia.org/id/occurrence/established> ;
  dct:source <https://www.doi.org/10.3391/ai.2017.12.1.11> .

<https://aphia.org/id/origin/alien> a skos:Concept, td:Origin ;
  skos:prefLabel "Alien"@en ;
  rdfs:label "Alien"@en ;
  skos:definition "Species introduced by man into places out of their natural range of distribution"@en .

<https://aphia.org/id/invasiveness/not-specified> a skos:Concept, td:Invasiveness ;
  skos:prefLabel "Not specified"@en ;
  rdfs:label "Not specified"@en ;
  skos:definition "A species whose 'invasiveness' has not been specified in its introduced range. The species is kn

<https://aphia.org/id/occurrence/established> a skos:Concept, td:Occurrence ;
  skos:prefLabel "Established"@en ;
  rdfs:label "Established"@en ;
  skos:definition "Species that have become established in their introduced range"@en .

```

Figure 17: Example of materialisation of data on species distribution

As shown in the Figure above, the distribution is identified by a URI where an identifier for distributions have been used. It is linked to the taxon (blank node) denoted by an accepted name and put together various elements of the distribution like the Origin, the Invasiveness, the Occurrence, materialised as SKOS controlled vocabularies (they are instances of `skos:Concept` in Figure 17). The example shows also the use of the marine regions linked open data through the property `hasArea`.

7 Concluding Remarks

This document describes the preliminary version of the ontologies developed during the first year of the MAREGRAPH project. The ontologies are organised in a network that was developed with a specific methodology, incorporated into the general organisational process introduced in WP2, which the document describes.

From the point of view of future development, the publication of this version of the ontologies is an important milestone for the project, as it enables the start of the LOD transformation work, part of the activities planned in the context of WP4 and WP5.

Furthermore, it allows us to initiate the validation and testing phase of the ontology development methodology by first examining the data from the WoRMS database. Indeed, we expect that there may be revisions to be applied to the ontology modules in order to arrive at the creation and publication of the final release, where the ontologies to be developed in the context of the EuROBIS domain will also be included and linked.

Internally, we have already discussed the possible enrichment of some of the modelling proposals introduced in this deliverable. Just as an example, the relationship between a Media Object and a Taxon seems potentially more complex than a simple subject relationship. There are other elements of the Taxon that can be described by the Media Object and this

probably requires the introduction of an RDF reification to represent a more articulated scenario.

Finally, another important element for semantic interoperability will be the production of controlled vocabularies; for this purpose, following the publication of this document, controlled vocabulary templates will be created to guide the LOD transformation of related database data according to the SKOS W3C Web standard.

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